

Skills 4 eosc

Milestone: Pilot Course for Undergraduate Students

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Deliverable Abstract

This is a short report on the pilot course for undergraduate students designed by the Skills4EOSC project, WP4, T4.3. The course content was planned to take advantage of the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Undergraduate Students, a competency profile developed within Skills4EOSC. The report summarises the pilot course and points to areas for improvement regarding the content based on the course feedback, and further, alignment with the MVS for Undergraduates.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset

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1 Executive summary

A pilot course on Open Science for undergraduate students was conducted at Tampere University, Finland, in the spring semester 2024. The course introduced undergraduate students to Open Science and research data management, providing them with the basic knowledge and skills needed in today's research environment for their studies and future careers.

The course was developed by Task 4.3 during the winter 2023-2024 and was opened to students at Tampere University in March 2024. It was based on earlier, well-established, open-learning materials, which were adapted and combined for this purpose. The course content was planned to take advantage of the MVS for Undergraduate Students.

The course consisted of six modules covering topics such as Open Science, Open Access, copyright and licensing, research data management, and research impact and visibility. It was offered as a self-paced online course in Moodle.

37 students participated in the pilot course. Comprehensive feedback was collected from the participants and is used to improve the course before reopening it to a wider audience. The feedback indicated a need for this type of course, which was considered very useful among the students.

2 Course description

2.1 Developing the course

The course was developed with the project partners during the winter 2023-2024. The work was based on earlier, well-established open learning materials, which were adapted and combined for this purpose. The course was developed in English, but was translated into Finnish for piloting. The course was piloted with undergraduate students at Tampere University in spring semester 2024. It was opened in March and closed at the end of July.

2.2 Course content

The course consists of six modules covering the topics Open Science, Open Access, copyright and licensing, research data management, and research impact and visibility. The course content was planned to take advantage of the MVS for Undergraduate Students. The content on copyright and licensing was adapted from Deliverable 3.6. by Luca Schirru¹. The chapters *Introduction to research management* and *Research data management in practice* were mainly formulated by Siiri Fuchs and Päivi Rauste from CSC.

During the course, students learned the key principles and goals of Open Science. They were taught how Open Access works and why making research as open as possible benefits everyone. The course also explained intellectual property, copyright, and open licensing, demonstrating how these concepts fit into Open Science. It emphasized the importance of managing data well and provided guidance on best practices. Additionally, students learned about research impact and strategies to increase the visibility and influence of research. The modules included texts, videos, and assignments.

¹ Schirru, L., Colcelli, V., Brizioli, S., Karabuga, E., Fernandes, E., & Margoni, T. (2023). D3.6 - Coordinated set of guides, fact-sheets and FAQs on ELSI aspects for Civil Servants and Policy Makers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7991444>

2.3 Alignment with MVS for Undergraduates

The course aligned with the MVS for Undergraduates² developed in the project (see Table 1).

Table 1 - The alignment between the MVS skills and competences and corresponding learning objectives in the course. (Note: Soft skills were not included, as they are not directly relevant to an online course.)

MVS Essential Skills and Competences	Corresponding learning objectives in the course
Organizing and documenting	understand the importance of research data management for research; understand what a proper data management plan includes and how tools can be used to develop one; be able to organise and document data appropriately; understand the concepts of metadata and persistent identifiers
Foundational digital research skills	understand the basic principles of data collection, including its reuse; identify reliable sources of reusable data
Understanding the big why - why it is important for society that research and data is open and FAIR	know the basic principles and objectives of Open Science; understand the historical background and development of Open Science; know the benefits and challenges of adopting Open Science practices; understand the importance of research data management and the FAIR principles for research
Knowledge of the research life cycle	understand the different stages of the research data life cycle and the related data management activities
Ability to identify general knowledge and awareness of open science and FAIR principles, including identify relevant discipline or domain-specific information	know the basic principles and objectives of Open Science; know the FAIR principles, and distinguish between FAIR data and open data

² Whyte, A., Green, D., Avanço, K., Di Giorgio, S., Gingold, A., Horton, L., Koteska, B., Kyprianou, K., Prnjat, O., Rauste, P., Schirru, L., Sowinski, C., Torres Ramos, G., van Leersum, N., Sharma, C., Méndez, E., & Lazzeri, E. (2023). D2.1 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles - Minimum Viable Skillsets (v1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8101903>

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Ability to apply basic open science principles in the relevant parts of the research life cycle, such as:	
– Recognise reliable and trustworthy sources of data	identify reliable sources of reusable data
– Evaluate the quality and reusability of the data	identify reliable sources of reusable data
– Recognizing the different open access models for scientific publications	understand the role of Open Access in scientific communication; understand what Open Access publishing means and the practices involved; identify the risks of predatory publishers; understand the benefits and challenges of open peer review
– Knowledge of how to share FAIR research data (including code and software), including knowledge of how to use repositories	identify sensitive data and understand its specifics in data management; understand how open source software works; understand the concepts of metadata and persistent identifiers; know the principles of publishing data from a FAIR perspective; understand the role of data repositories in data preservation and sharing

The course also includes learning objectives that extend beyond the MVS. As part of the co-creation process for the MVS, this task also reported to Task 2.6 (responsible for the co-creation process), on the learning objectives implemented beyond the MVS. This feedback was used to further develop the MVS. The learning objectives that went beyond the MVS were:

- understand the basic concepts of intellectual property and copyright and their importance in scientific work
- identify the principles of open licensing and the uses and implications of open licenses
- know what is meant by the research impact
- know the different types of impact indicators and how they work
- understand the importance of research visibility and know different ways to increase the visibility of research

2.4 Participants

37 students participated in the course. The students were bachelor students, mainly from information studies. The course was elective for them. The course was promoted to the students through the Tampere University Intranet.

3 Feedback

3.1 Feedback questionnaire

The students were required to complete a feedback questionnaire at the end of each module, and a final questionnaire at the end of whole course. The questionnaires included mostly multiple-choice questions and statements.

After each question, there was also an open field where the students were able to justify their answers.

3.2 Roses

First of all, students felt that they achieved the learning goals very well (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 - How well do you think you achieved the learning objectives of the course?

Overall, the course was well received and considered relevant and useful (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 - The content of the course was relevant and useful

The course was found to be well structured and understandable.

“As its name indicates, the course focused on open science and opened up many aspects of its details. It went down to a practical level, which helped to grasp and assimilate new issues.”

Most of the students liked that the course materials included both text and videos, and the variety of assignments was also appreciated.

“For me, learning was particularly enhanced by the fact that there were many different ways of learning. There were videos and texts, and the tasks were varied. I found that the variety kept me interested.”

The course got a very good overall grade (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 - Give the course an overall grade

All in all, feedback shows that there is a need for this type of course.

“I think this course would be a good addition to any curriculum and for any university student.”

“I found it useful to learn about this topic, as I had not come across any courses on the subject myself. Open science was an interesting and important topic.”

3.3 Room for improvement

The main issue with the course was that it was not broad enough for a five-credit course (see Fig. 4). The reason why it should have been five credits is that Tampere University prefers all courses to be 5 credits (or 10, 15 etc.).

Fig. 4 - In terms of credits, the workload of the course was...

Why it was not broad enough was partly because we did not require for the pilot course participants to write a learning diary, which will be part of the course later. In the pilot course we replaced it with the feedback questionnaires, which naturally made the workload a bit lighter.

"The assignments in some sections were quite quick and easy, even though I was looking for more information on them. Perhaps the assignments could be extended further, but on the other hand, a learning diary in the future will certainly increase the workload on the course."

Differences in the size of the modules were also pointed out.

"Perhaps I would have preferred more balance between the sections, so to speak, because some of them were longer and some shorter."

Some smaller issues were also raised, including the need for clarification of certain concepts, more information on specific topics, and further details about the assignments, such as word counts. Additionally, there were some practical issues related to the e-learning platform Moodle.

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The students were also allowed to suggest ideas for topics they would like to see covered in the course. The students suggested topics like the impact of AI on Open Science and Open Science from the students' perspective.

It is also worth noting that while many liked the opportunity to work independently on their own pace, it is not for everyone, and the possibility to discuss with others could contribute to learning.

“It would have been interesting to exchange views with students from different disciplines and to hear how Open Science is seen in different disciplines. At the same time, some of the more difficult topics would probably have been opened up more.”

4 Conclusions and next steps

There is a need for an Open Science course among undergraduate students. Feedback from the pilot course shows that the topic is considered important by students.

Based on the feedback, the course will be developed with partners during autumn 2024. The finalised course will be published in spring 2025 and the materials of the course will be openly available to all. This course strongly advances the Skills4EOSC core objective for the undergraduate degree to promote Open Science skills and integrate existing training to a common and trusted pan-European ecosystem.